

Comparative Analysis of Consumer Behaviour toward Sport Shoes and Casual Shoes in Punjab

Sonam Sood
Research Scholar
IKG PTU.

Dr. Vikramjit Kaur
Associate professor
Rayat institute of management, SBS

Abstract:- The shoes are considered as a source of generating an impression on others and in today's scenario maintaining a better impression on others is one of the major components and crucial factors for creating a better first impression. Since all human beings are social animals so they are quite concerned about their social impression and want to create the best impression in the minds of people. The researchers have stated that footwear is considered as the most attractive and most vital part when the issue is related to the fitness of the person and most of the running activities can only be improved and done by wearing the best shoes. As per the study and researches, it has been identified that there are various shoes which are present in the market for the customers and they can easily choose the best quality product as per their requirements. In this paper main research is performed on the basis of comparative analysis of consumer behaviour towards sports shoes and casual shoes in Punjab.

I. INTRODUCTION

Comfort, health and style is perhaps the first three things that comes to mind when you hear the word "shoes". The awareness regarding health among Indians can be understood by the ever increasing percentage of gymnasiums and sports centre over the period of last 10 years. This growth can be associated with the impact of media and this indeed has brought bountiful positives to the physical well being of Indians.

The major sector benefitting from this awareness regarding health among Indians is the sports shoe industry. People cannot satisfy their health related needs in the absence of an adequate pair of shoes. The sports shoes industry as a result of it is earning great deal of money. Now a day due to the fashion consciousness and style people prefer casual shoes as everyone wants to look perfect. Most of the top brands deals in both sport shoes as well as casual shoes. The average annual turnover that the shoe industry fetches in India lies approximately between Rs. 3500 crore and Rs. 5000 crore. The undisputed king of this market is Reebok. It had been observed from the researches that even though there is not brand dilution but people seem confused regarding brands. A general consumer fails to draw distinction between various sports brands such as Nike, Adidas and Reebok. The only brand that has been able to establish and make a distinguished identity is the puma. It manages to do by designing an altogether different pattern which is sleek than other shoes.

Shoes worn by Indians are not only as a matter of fitness or taking part in sports activities but they are adorned with casual clothing too. This is the reason Reebok has fetched a huge market share.

II. WHY STUDYING CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR?

The aim of study consumer behaviour is to predict consumer responses in market. The success of a company thrives on understanding its customers. The identification of wants of consumers and their fulfilment is the driving force for success. There is unstopped purchasing by consumer of various products without even actually realising its usage and this purchase is deliberate just to enjoy the new brands without getting information regarding product. The consumer cannot be blamed for that too as the market is flooded with products and it is not possible for him to study the features and usage of each product. Consumer buying decisions depend on him. Whereas the markets offers/ fulfils his needs. Therefore, the entire focus is on identification of his requirements.

According to kotler (1994) consumer study answers the buying patterns involving what, who, when and why he purchases a product. (Kotler, 1994) is amalgamation of various branches of study such as psychology, anthropology, economics, sociology and social anthropology. The decision taken by buyer solely and in groups are attempted to study here. There can be various factors that affect consumers' buying behaviour and all this such as demographic, psychographic and behavioural variables are investigated under it. The influencing groups for example, family friends, reference groups and society in general , to epitomize, at the time of buying shoes the customers chooses it as per the family decision , comfort, satisfaction and price quality. Even in one same family, the choices of people vary that is, variation of buying behaviour in one family (Kotler, Marketing Management, 2009). The study is aimed at finding the horizons of consumer behaviour while purchasing sport shoes and casual shoes. It also envisions the factors affecting consumers' buying decision of sport shoes and casual shoes.

The identification of consumer behaviour is the foundation of studying consumer buying behaviour. Consumer purchases a product due to infinite factors. Consumer buying behaviour concerns with modern marketing philosophy – identify consumers' needs and satisfy them more effectively than competitors to ensure long term survival in the market. . Marketing becomes consumer oriented with modern marketing approach that involves identification of customer's requirements and

fulfilling more effectively than competitors. This is the key of success. When the organisation succeeds in recognizing consumer needs and fulfilling them prior and better than counterparts, a company is successful survive, earn more profits and grow in a highly competitive marketing environment. Hence, marketing objectives can be achieved through studying consumer's behaviour. It offers benefits to multiple parties including company as well as mediators and salesmen because they can be successful in fulfilling customer requirements and wants. The performance of the entire distribution system is improved with consumer behaviour (money matters, 2017). It is easier to prepare marketing programme with appropriate focus on product, price, promotion and distribution systems. There is better presentation of programme when it is focused on consumer behaviour. There are great variations market which can be felt in requirements and demand of every section. There is a need of separate marketing programme for every segment. Several group of buyers can be supplied with varied offers only through knowledge of consumer differentiation. Consumer behaviour study helps to know regarding consumer differentiation. This also assists in projecting the potential requirements of market. There is sufficient time with marketer to discover prospective opportunities as well as to be prepared for upcoming threats and challenges. Facing competition is also eased with study of consumer behaviour. The marketer is able to offer higher benefits as per consumer's expectations. This ultimately makes the competitive strength of company better. The changing aspects of market are studied by consumer behaviour. This will eventually make a manger dynamic, alert and active so that he understood the consumer better and earlier than competitors. (jaideep, 2016)

The market pattern can be checked effectively by study of consumer behaviour. Consumer behaviour study is indispensable to analyse the present as well as future needs to boost sales. It is based on the assumption that consumer responds positively to organisation's needs when his needs are fulfilled. The solution to almost all the problems is study of consumer behaviour. It is not possible to carry out the latest marketing practices without studying the behaviour of consumer.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE-PREVIOUS STUDIES

A revolution of analytical subjects of information in hand as well as systematic techniques on a specific issue is studied under the body of literature review. These resources are study of already existing sources and the investigator is not review is primarily aimed at making the reader aware of ideas that have already been discussed and developing a base for some new objective which may be prospective research required and not yet done in that filed. There are prodigious features of an appropriate literature review. It entails a systematic step by step presentation of relevant points; recent and useful references with suitable referencing pattern, accurate utilization of terms and an unprejudiced and detailed vision of the former research on the same theme.

For clear and easy understanding, the review of literature is presented in the following headings

- Consumer behaviour
- Consumer behaviour in footwear industry
- Indian footwear industry

A. Consumer behaviour

The activity, thoughts arising in the mind of consumer, result that he is expecting out of his purchase in association with relative environment while taking his purchase decision that affect his purchase are all collectively termed as consumer behaviour (Krugman, Autumn, 1965). The environment beyond the control of buyer, the attributes of the location to which he belongs and buyer's own traits such as beliefs, values and attitudes are a few parameters affecting consumer behaviour.

Another definition states consumer behaviour as the procedure of understanding, scanning and examining the various factors related to buying. He further identifies two major heads that affect his choice. The very first constitute his requirements awareness regarding the features of brands and knowledge regarding presence of other options play a key role in his decision taking rest are the demographics of customer, his way of living and his own features. The second one is the environment which comprises reference groups, culture and social class. (Assael, 1994)

Deviation or alteration in any of this can have a major bearing on customers decision regarding brand and choice of good. Consumer behaviour is sum total of all activities beginning from purchases, utilization and discarding of goods or services. But, this terminology does not study the continuity of operations (Roger D. Blackwell, 2006). Covering the flaws of this definition, (Eric J. Arnould, 2004) coined another definition of consumer behaviour. He suggested the ongoing flow of consumption which identifies the procedures involved in purchasing as loops, which include, attainment, usage and dumping of goods and services put to use. The ultimate decision of consumer is undertaken after 7 steps and this is known as consumer decision model. This entails realization of requirement for any product or service, finding the relevant information thereof, prior buying, studying the pros and cons as well as benefits and applications, actual buying, its usage, studying its usability after usage and disinvestment (Roger D. Blackwell, 2006).

Rayport and jaworski ,unveiled that these 7 steps are t he fundamental of consumer research. They also explained the interdependence and independent effect of each of these steps on purchaser's decision. They also make sure to not to eliminate the significance of internet. Although it is very new, still it has taken over the well-established catalogue and tv shopping. (Jeffrey F. Rayport, 2004)

The organization need to adopt various strategies to allure customers. This may include reduced prices or attractive offers that outweigh products or services which competitors are offering. Stage 4 thus envisages the final

purchase by consumer once he has done comparative analysis of various retailers.

Kotler, simplify pre-purchase as the thorough investigation undertaken by buyer before his final decision. This stage entails paying focus to major requirements and matching them with actual features of product. These characteristics generally include price, size, quality and quantity. (Philip Kotler, 2006)

According to Solomon and Margaret the consumer behaviour is determined but the motivating forces affecting his choice while he makes his purchase decision. These motivations are often a result of his wishes. In addition, the customer does not want to disclose his motivations or he is also found to be unaware regarding the matter of fact that this entire research of his buying behaviour is aimed at determining what he is as a consumer and what he might become in future as a consumer. (Michael R. Solomon, 2006)

Blackwell further clarifies it by dividing the decision taking procedure under two broad heads. These are the retailer and in store selection. The customer evaluates a number of retailers from prior phase by his various features which he offers as a retailer whereas; the in-store selection comprises the salesmanship presentation of the articles of shop and buying none at the specific time. (Roger D. Blackwell, 2006)

Kapferer in 2008 made a remarkable research by explaining that appearance of product does not matter to the buyer if he is loyal to the brand. (Kapferer, 2008)

Branding ensures stability and consistency to the buyer. The brand is for more stationary than the variety of products. The buyer does not generally shift from the brand once he has developed a sense of commitment towards it. This is where it becomes imperative to learn why consumer refuses to attain / buy and product or brand.

The modern market has been found to be traditional as well as extremely competitive by Saravanan in his research in 2010. As the consumer is deemed to be king of market, the entire marketing strategies revolve round him. This is the basis of consumer behaviour research. The contemporary epoch is witnesses by the dominance of females in all fields and the significant decision regarding purchase of non-durables rely on them. (Dr.S.Saravanan, 2010)

For acquiring the relevant target group, it is must to have thorough information regarding buyer behaviour and his buying habits . Besides, he also explains that the target audience of each organization varies and the organization needs to be clever in devising a suitable approach capable of fetching maximum target group. (Michael R. Solomon, 2006). The variations in consumer behaviour are a result of age, sex, profession, earning, culture or ethnic differences and his habits as well as areas of interest also have a major bearing on the same. A striking feature is that there can be similarities in some of the cases. Solomon is at same pace with (J. Paul Peter, 2010)who claim that in dynamic

environment, consumer is also dynamic with his decisions. Thus, the marketing strategies have to be altered according.

IV. CONSUMER DECISION MAKING MODELS

The consumer decision making models are being devised for the last 50 years based on different economic and psychological fields.

A. Nicosia model (1966)

Nicosia, first of all, came up with model of purchase behaviour. There are four segments in this model. First one is, communicating knowledge to direct his thinking and this comes as a result of characteristics of company and features of customer, mainly predispositions of customer. After this, there is identification and judgement procedure, a decision and finally results that come in the form of behaviour, utilization, storage, experience and feedback. The motive of nicosia's model behind inclusion of repurchase cycle is formation of conceptual framework which is primary indispensable for services. Generally when it comes to finance related services (such as banking service or financial planning advice), customers tend to stick to same service provider over the years. Along with this, there are risks in terms of money or simply psychological risks which restrict a buyer from switching his provides. This calls for requirement of feedback or repurchase loop in cdm model.(NICOSIA, 1966)

This model suffers from the drawback that it is based on marketer's point of view instead of that of customers. Customer has only defined through his activities. There is much less research that substantiate the model but there is enough research signaling the invalidity of model. (Tuck, 1976)

B. Engel, koliat and blackwell model (1968)

The shortcomings of nicosia's model were overcome by engle, koliat and blackwell in the late 1960s. (Engel, Kollat, & Blackwell, 1968)among the many positives one is that it has provision for repetition of incomplete decision making. To exemplify, even after going through all the steps of purchase process, the consumer can change his mind and quit the purchase decision. The decision making process can also have a situation where the buyer has no motive of buying and this obstructs his purchase process which is utilized for future reference. The typical examples of this are window shopping or participation in financial seminar without actually having any plans to invest. However, it can be studied as the buyer may use it for his prospective buying or he became incapable to complete the process or there can be some more important thing need to be undertaken which halted the process.

C. Howard and sheth model, 1969

The howard and sheth model is one level up than the other models. It is more precise as it encompasses that along with attitude, the other predominating factor affecting purchase is intention (Pappas, august 1972)both being variable factors. Another dominant feature of the model is that it envisages a wide variety of inputs in the marketing

variables and social influences which form to be a crucial bridge in the existing input – process – output models.

This model shows that information passes through four major components. These are inputs (marketing and social stimuli), perceptual constructs (attention and information search), learning constructs (aims, choice parameters, brand value resulting in perception, confidence, intention and contentment) and outputs (purchase, intention, brand comprehension, attitude and attention) (John A. Howard, 1969) there are external factors too which are taken up as fifth component and these include relevance of the purchase, background of customer, reference groups, characteristics of personality, availability of time and economic competence. These instead of being considered as part of information flow are considered as perceptual and learning constructs.

The howard and sheth (1969) model definitely explores, studies, investigates, evaluates and understand that there are multiple internal as well as external factors affecting consumer decision making process. Many uncovered aspects like attitude development, predisposition and time along with comprehensive inclusion of perceptual and learning theories were made a part of model. In contrast, the only limitation of this model is its complex nature.

V. FOOTWEAR INDUSTRY IN INDIA

In India, footwear kept on performing great in 2016, recording retail current esteem growth of 16% to achieve offers of INR 553 billion. The real footwear players in the indian market are confronting expanding rivalry from the web retailing channel, which offers countless brands. What's more, despite the fact that the real footwear mark makers have additionally made their items accessible through online retailers, their net revenues have taken a hit because of the substantial rebates offered by web retailers. (Euromonitor, 2017)

Indian footwear industry rank second-biggest footwear maker after china. In India production is approx. 13% of world footwear creation, which is near 16 billion pairs. This implies the normal utilization globally is around 2-3 pairs/individual. India produces rough 2,000 million pairs yearly in various classifications of footwear. India sends out around 115 million pairs, therefore almost 95% of its create takes care of its own local demand. With an expected global populace of 7-8 billion, india constitutes an offer of approx 15%, which implies 1.2 to 1.3 billion feet should be secured from warm, frosty, wounds, assurance and so on. Footwear part is an extremely noteworthy fragment of leather and non-leather items in India. Size of Indian domestic footwear industry is assessed to be worth 20-25,000 crore where footwear per capita utilization is evaluated to be approx 1.1 pairs. Moreover, slippers (hawaichappals) fragment is near 10000 crore with per capita utilization are evaluated to be 1 pairs. (Gupta, 2014)

Footwear in India kept on being driven by Bata India in 2016 with a retail esteem offer of 5%. The organization intends to open 100 new stores amid 2017. In 2016, bata concentrated on enhancing the operational effectiveness of

its current stores so as to build gainfulness and better serve shoppers. The organization is likewise concentrating on expanding its quality in littler third-and fourth-level urban areas and in addition achieving more shoppers through the web based retailing channel. Interest for footwear is relied upon to stay solid over the estimated time frame. The classification is expected to enlist a retail esteem cagr of 7% at steady 2016 costs, with deals achieving INR 778 billion of every 2021. The key drivers of growth will be optimistic shoppers from littler third-and fourth-level urban areas as more marked footwear ends up noticeably available to them because of store-based development and web retailing. (Euromonitor, 2017)

Developing at a compound yearly growth rate (cagr) of around 15%, the indian footwear industry is probably going to reach about Rs 38,700 crore by 2015 from the present level of about Rs 22,000 crore, as per industry load Assocham. India creates almost 300 crore pairs of footwear every year, sends out more than 10% and represents around 15% of yearly global footwear generation which is more than 2,000 crore, as indicated by a study titled 'indian footwear industry: an analysis' the domestic footwear showcase is driven by developing design consciousness together with expanded extra cash among india's urban white collar class which contributes around 45% of general footwear advertise, making india the second-biggest global maker of footwear crosswise over differed sections after china," ds rawat, secretary general of assocham, said while discharging the discoveries. (Doval, 2015)

Indian footwear market is developing a result of customer will spend more on different segments like formals, sportswear, casuals, adventure wear, home wear, beachwear, wedding wear, lounge wear, club wear and so forth 55% of the whole business involves men's footwear, 30 percent for women and 15% for kids. So it is very certain the men overwhelm the shoe business. The people of India appear to have an interest towards shoes that have an alternate styling to it. With the approach of the current era, the people appear to have made a significant adjustment to their styling requests. People appear to be seriously connected with the styling needs these days since when it comes down to the shoes, one can't just let go the fashion. (Nagrle, 2015) Some popular brands are Bata, Nike, Reebok, Liberty, Converse, Woodland, Puma, Adidas, Red tape, Relaxo, Action, Lotto, Fila, Lancer, Red chief, and Valentine.

VI. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The purpose of this research is to examine the consumer behaviour toward the sport shoes and casual shoes and what factors make the difference in sport shoes and casual shoes purchase intentions. Factors included (1) demographic and shopping behaviour variables: age, income, qualification, gender, marital status, quantity of shoes own, shoes purchased frequency, price of shoes, locations of store, and shopping frequency. (2) Psychological factors attitude, perception, personality; and (3) shoes attributes: trend and style, colour, material, brand

name, comfort, durability, and service. The primary objectives of study are:

- To study the present status of Indian footwear industry
- To find out the influence of demographic variables such as gender, age, income level and occupation. A relationship towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- To study the factors motivating people to purchase sport shoes over the casual shoes
- to assess the level of importance given to the certain factors such as price, durability, qualities etc. by the customer while taking purchase of branded casual shoes and sport shoes according to their occupational status
- To find out the desirable factors for expectation of customers in future

VII. HYPOTHESIS

The following are the certain assumptions for the proposed after the analysis of literature:

H0: There is no significant relationship of gender towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

- H1: There is significant relationship of gender towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- H2: There is no significant relationship of age towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- H3: There is significant relationship of age towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- H4: There is no significant relationship of occupational towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- H5: There is significant relationship of occupational towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

VIII. SIGNIFICANCE AND SCOPE OF STUDY

The purpose of this study is to contribute to a better knowledge of consumer buying behaviour towards purchasing the sports shoes and casual shoes. The aim of the research is to find out the factors influencing the consumer behaviour while purchasing sports shoes and casual shoes. The research will help in segmenting consumers based on various factors like gender preferences, spending patterns, trend consciousness, and fashion consciousness.

With this study, it mainly focuses on the consumers of Punjab state. The primary data will be collected from the consumers (equal number of males and females) from Punjab. The secondary data will also be used when requires from journals, books and article etc.

IX. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A large scope of literature, providing a complex academic background about the consumer behaviour, pointed to the suitability of using deduction as a research outlook. The aim of the research is to gather information from wide scale of footwear consumers and deduce specifics applicable to an individual.

A. Research design

The research design which is used while conducting this research is descriptive research whose main objective is to get the accurate answers from the respondents. The most common method of collecting quantitative data survey has been chosen for the research. Due to a principle of research designed to discover consumers' buying behaviour toward shoe shopping, which is turned out to be an appropriate way of gathering data. The literature review has provided valuable secondary data describing a chosen area.

B. Sample selection

The probability technique is used to select the samples. The consumers were randomly selected from various cities of Punjab and the total sample size is 100 respondents.

C. Data collection

For primary data questionnaires is used as an instrument to get the data from the customers/ consumers. A social network has been selected as a primary distribution channel. The questionnaire which is created is sent out via the email client. The collection of data has been carried out in famous markets and in a shopping centre. Secondary it is derived from various sources like internet, online internet articles, Journals and other marketing management, consumer behaviour books and literatures.

D. Tools and Techniques used for Analysis

Statistical tools like frequency distribution, percentages and statistical techniques like chi-square test and KMO and Bartlett's test is used to test the association between the variables.

X. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Objective 1: To study the present status of the Indian footwear industry.

- a. What the India footwear industry actually includes?
 - Manufacture
 - Design
 - Production
 - Sales of shoes.
- b) What are the basis of segmentation of the foot ware industry in India?
 - Athletic and non –athletic shoes
 - Men's, women's and children's shoes and
 - Online and retail distribution channels.
- c) What type of integrated marketing strategy used by the footwear manufacturers?
 - use a mix of traditional
 - Social and digital media as well as
 - Innovative techniques such as crowd sourcing.
- d) Major footwear companies in India?
 - Nike
 - Adidas
 - Action
 - Reebok

- e) Major focus of footwear industry in India is on
 - Improving quality
 - Reducing wastage
 - Reduce adverse environmental impact

➤ Ha: There is significant relationship of gender towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

B. Objective 2: To find out the influence of demographic variables such as gender, age, income level and occupation, a relationship towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

- a) What is your gender? *
 - Male
 - Female

- Hypothesis:
 - H0: There is no significant relationship of gender towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

Crosstab Count

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total	
		A	B	C	D	E		
What is your gender?		295	0	0	0	0	0	295
	A	0	111	145	51	83	148	538
	B	0	96	116	63	56	128	459
	C	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total		295	208	261	114	139	276	1293

Table 1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1305.765 ^a	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	1397.953	15	.000
N of Valid Cases	1293		

Table 2

a. 6 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.005	.000
	Cramer's V	.580	.000
N of Valid Cases		1293	

Table 3

From the Pearson chi-square test, as p value is less than 0.01, it can be concluded that there is significant relationship of gender towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis. In sense, it implies that gender of a person will decide which type of footwear they would like to purchase. Similar conclusion can also be drawn from Phi and Crammer’s v test at 1% level of significance that a strong association exists between gender and choice on the purchase of shoes.

- b) How old are you?
 - 16-25
 - 25-34
 - 34-44
 - 45-54
 - 55 +
- H0: There is no significant relationship of age towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
- Ha: There is significant relationship of age towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
How old are you?		295	0	0	0	0	295
	A	0	52	63	27	43	250
	B	0	74	79	39	46	327
	C	0	59	82	27	34	286
	D	0	14	25	12	11	83
E	0	9	12	9	5	52	
Total		295	208	261	114	139	276

Table 4

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1307.927 ^a	25	.000
Likelihood Ratio	1400.083	25	.000
N of Valid Cases	1293		

Table 5

b. 1 cells (2.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.58.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.006	.000
	Cramer's V	.450	.000
N of Valid Cases		1293	

Table 6

From the Pearson chi-square test, as p value is less than 0.01, it can be concluded that there is significant relationship of age towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis. In sense, it implies that age of a person will decide which type of footwear they would like to purchase. Similar conclusion can also be drawn from Phi and Crammer’s v test at 1% level of significance that a strong association is existing between age and choice on the purchase of shoes.

- c) What are your occupational statuses?
- Student
 - Employee/Self-employer
 - Maternity leave/Unemployed
 - Retired
 - H0: There is no significant relationship of occupational towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.
 - Ha: There is significant relationship of occupational towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis.

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
What are your occupational statuses?		295	0	0	0	0	295
	A	0	46	73	36	42	282
	B	0	87	109	42	58	398
	C	0	55	60	28	28	233
	D	0	20	19	8	11	85
Total		295	208	261	114	139	276

Table 7

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1304.321 ^a	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	1397.711	20	.000
N of Valid Cases	1293		

Table 8

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.49.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.004	.000
	Cramer's V	.502	.000
N of Valid Cases		1293	

Table 9

From the Pearson chi-square test, as p value is less than 0.01, it can be concluded that there is significant relationship of occupation towards fashion on purchase of sport shoes and casual basis. In sense, it implies that occupation of a person will decide which type of footwear they would like to purchase. Similar conclusion can also be drawn from Phi and Cramer's v test at 1% level of significance that a strong association exists between occupation and choice on the purchase of shoes.

- d) What is your marital status?
 - Single
 - Married/in permanent relationship
 - Divorced
 - Widowed
- e) Which of these quotes fits you the most? Please choose max. 2 answers
 - I am very alert to changes in men's/women's fashion.
 - I would say that I am very fashion conscious.
 - Other people think I am fashionable/trendy.
 - I read magazines that have fashion/style pages.
 - I usually shop only in trendy stores.
 - I am conscious about how my outfit looks at work/school.
 - I am consciousness of the latest trends but I do not shop due to them
 - I am very price conscious when it comes to fashion.
 - I do not care about the latest fashion trends. I buy what I like.
 - I do not think much about my outfit.
 - I let other people to advise me about fashion.
 - Other: Shoe shopping motivators and habits.

C. Objective 3 – To study the factors motivating people to purchase sport shoes over the casual shoes

- a) What are the different types of shoes available?
 - Sandals (casual sandals, dress sandals, etc)
 - Boots (dress boots, work boots, hiking/recreational boots, etc)
 - Pumps (designer pumps, classic pumps, heels, etc.)
 - Sneakers (fitness sneakers, running sneakers, casual sneakers, etc)
 - Slippers
- b) What is/are decisive factor/s when shoe shopping?
 - Price
 - Quality
 - a unique style
 - Brand
 - Comfort/The fit of shoes
- c) Do you think weight is a factor for choosing a particular type of shoes?
 - Yes
 - No
- d) How do you consider the importance of sports shoes?
 - Durability
 - Fitness purpose
 - Comfortable level
 - Running or jogging purpose
 - Sole of the shoes
 - Attractive design /colour

Case Processing Summary

	Cases		Missing		Total	
	Valid N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Durability * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%
Fitness purpose * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%
Comfortable level * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%
Running or jogging purpose * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%
Sole of the shoes * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%
Attractive design /colour * What are the different type of shoes are available?	997	95.2%	50	4.8%	1047	100.0%

Table 10

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Durability	1	71	102	87	27	29	316
	2	62	71	67	17	19	236
	3	29	45	34	20	12	140
	4	50	61	52	21	10	194
	5	31	35	24	15	6	111
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 11

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.316 ^a	16	.575
Likelihood Ratio	14.424	16	.567
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 12

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.46.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.120	.575
	Cramer's V	.060	.575
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 13

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Fitness purpose	strongly agree	79	100	86	44	24	333
	agree	101	119	96	31	33	380
	neutral	31	36	33	6	9	115
	disagree	20	43	31	16	9	119
	strongly disagree	12	16	18	3	1	50
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 14

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.436 ^a	16	.247
Likelihood Ratio	20.745	16	.189
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 15

a. 1 cells (4.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.81.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.140	.247
	Cramer's V	.070	.247
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 16

Crosstab

Count

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Comfortable level	strongly agree	83	108	93	28	18	330
	agree	56	84	54	31	19	244
	neutral	28	43	45	15	10	141
	disagree	50	53	54	15	20	192
	strongly disagree	26	26	18	11	9	90
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 17

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.402 ^a	16	.301
Likelihood Ratio	18.510	16	.295
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 18

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.86.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.136	.301
	Cramer's V	.068	.301
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 19

Crosstab

Count

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Running or jogging purpose	strongly agree	73	101	76	27	25	302
	agree	46	65	61	22	17	211
	neutral	60	58	46	28	11	203
	disagree	35	52	50	12	12	161
	strongly disagree	29	38	31	11	11	120
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 20

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.644 ^a	16	.625
Likelihood Ratio	13.466	16	.638
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 21

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.15.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.117	.625
	Cramer's V	.058	.625
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 22

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Sole of the shoes	strongly agree	75	133	100	38	34	380
	agree	63	80	66	35	21	265
	neutral	42	49	41	13	9	154
	disagree	37	27	30	8	5	107
	strongly disagree	26	25	27	6	7	91
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 23

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.874 ^a	16	.183
Likelihood Ratio	20.785	16	.187
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 24

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.94.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.145	.183
	Cramer's V	.072	.183
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 25

**Crosstab
Count**

		What are the different type of shoes are available?					Total
		A	B	C	D	E	
Attractive design /colour	strongly agree	31	57	46	15	8	157
	agree	60	78	53	25	16	232
	neutral	58	84	68	30	24	264
	disagree	69	54	56	21	16	216
	strongly disagree	25	41	41	9	12	128
Total		243	314	264	100	76	997

Table 26

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.675 ^a	16	.191
Likelihood Ratio	20.746	16	.188
N of Valid Cases	997		

Table 27

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.76.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.144	.191
	Cramer's V	.072	.191
N of Valid Cases		997	

Table 28

In order to know that which factor is really important for sport shoes to be purchased is that although all factors are affecting but affect is not statistically significant.

D. Objective 4: To assess the level of importance given to the certain factors such as price, durability, qualities etc. by the customer while taking purchase of branded casual shoes and sport shoes according to their occupational status

- a) How many pair of shoes have you got?
 - Less than 5
 - Between 5 and 10
 - Between 10 and 20
 - More than 20 but not more than 50
 - 50+
- b) How often do you buy footwear?
 - More than once a month
 - Once a month
 - Once every three months
 - Once every six months
 - Once a year
 - Less than once a year
 - I never buy shoes
- c) Why do you buy new footwear? Please check max. 3 answers
 - Because I need to replace worn out shoes
 - To reward myself

- I need to find something comfortable
- Because they were on Sale/ promotion
- Because the season was changing
- To match a new outfit
- To keep up with the latest fashions
- To impress my friends
- For a special occasion, e.g. party, wedding
- It is simply fun!
- None of these

- d) Do you have a favorite footwear brand?
 - Yes
 - No
- e) What stimulates your brand loyalty? Please check max. 2 answers
 - Relevant and wide offer
 - Reasonable prices
 - What other people think about the brand
 - Quality of services provided/Helpful personnel
 - Previous positive experience
 - A recommendation of salespeople
 - Advice of spouse or a relative
 - Prestige of the brand

Case Processing Summary

	Cases Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
A. Relevant and wide offer * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
B. Reasonable prices * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
C. What other people think about the brand * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
D. Quality of services provided/Helpful personnel * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
E. Previous positive experience * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
F. A recommendation of salespeople * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
G. Advice of spouse or a relative * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%
H. Prestige of the brand * What are your occupational statuses?	999	91.3%	95	8.7%	1094	100.0%

Table 29

Crosstab Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
A. Relevant and wide offer	strongly agree	104	165	91	27	387
	agree	64	91	47	21	223
	neutral	43	37	24	9	113
	disagree	27	62	38	16	143
	strongly disagree	45	43	33	12	133
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 30

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.612 ^a	12	.098
Likelihood Ratio	18.909	12	.091
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 31

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.61.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.136	.098
	Cramer's V	.079	.098
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 32

Crosstab
Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
B. Reasonable prices	strongly agree	79	121	73	22	295
	agree	78	106	66	22	272
	neutral	77	106	54	20	257
	disagree	30	44	26	14	114
	strongly disagree	19	21	14	7	61
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 33

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.713 ^a	12	.930
Likelihood Ratio	5.474	12	.940
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 34

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.19.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.076	.930
	Cramer's V	.044	.930
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 35

Crosstab
Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
C. What other people think about the brand	strongly agree	90	115	63	36	304
	agree	49	87	49	14	199
	neutral	52	77	40	11	180
	disagree	65	69	51	16	201
	strongly disagree	27	50	30	8	115
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 36

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.568 ^a	12	.266
Likelihood Ratio	14.420	12	.275
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 37

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.78.

Crosstab
Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
D. Quality of services	strongly agree	97	127	79	27	330

provided/Helpful personnel	agree	68	101	37	20	226
	neutral	62	74	52	18	206
	disagree	42	67	46	16	171
	strongly disagree	14	29	19	4	66
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 38

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.760 ^a	12	.387
Likelihood Ratio	13.357	12	.344
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 39

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.62.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.113	.387
	Cramer's V	.065	.387
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 40

Crosstab Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
E. Previous positive experience	strongly agree	67	110	50	26	253
	agree	77	108	73	17	275
	neutral	48	80	48	22	198
	disagree	50	49	22	8	129
	strongly disagree	41	51	40	12	144
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 41

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.273 ^a	12	.082
Likelihood Ratio	19.078	12	.087
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 42

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.98.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.139	.082
	Cramer's V	.080	.082
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 43

Crosstab Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
F. A recommendation of salespeople	strongly agree	58	68	52	18	196
	agree	68	103	60	25	256
	neutral	33	41	23	7	104
	disagree	71	117	58	25	271
	strongly disagree	53	69	40	10	172
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 44

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.661 ^a	12	.811
Likelihood Ratio	7.853	12	.797
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 45

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.85.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.510 ^a	12	.659
Likelihood Ratio	9.539	12	.656
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 46

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.21.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.098	.659
	Cramer's V	.056	.659
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 47

Crosstab

Count

		What are your occupational statuses?				Total
		A	B	C	D	
H. Prestige of the brand	strongly agree	92	97	70	28	287
	agree	62	105	52	21	240
	neutral	42	62	42	10	156
	disagree	58	89	46	21	214
	strongly disagree	29	45	23	5	102
Total		283	398	233	85	999

Table 48

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.300 ^a	12	.503
Likelihood Ratio	11.646	12	.475
N of Valid Cases	999		

Table 49

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.68.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.106	.503
	Cramer's V	.061	.503
N of Valid Cases		999	

Table 50

In order to assess the level of importance given to the certain factors such as price, durability, qualities etc. by the customer while taking purchase of branded casual shoes and sport shoes according to their occupational status. Thus, factors i.e previous positive experience and relevant wide offer have a significant association according to the different occupational status of individual to determine at 10% level

of significance. The same result can be seen from descriptive statistics.

f) Which of these statements fits you the most? Please check max. 2 answers

- I am willing to pay higher price for the guarantee of quality
- Price is a crucial determinant for me
- I buy from a few retailers that i know and trust
- It is hard to find shoes which are both stylish and comfortable
- I tend to buy the same brands
- I preferred shoes which are made in Britain
- I have problems with finding shoes which fits me
- I shop in stores offering Sales/ promotion
- I do not mind to pay a high price for well-known/luxury brands

E. Objective 5 - to find out the desirable factors for expectation of customers in future

- a) Are you satisfied with the current services of footwear industry?
- Highly satisfied
 - Moderate
 - Low satisfied
 - Not at all
- b) What kind of extra benefits you prefer?
- Lucky coupon

- Free gift
- Discount
- Buy one get one free

c) What kind of Improvement you want in features of shoes?

- Attractive sole
- Reasonable price
- High quality
- Comfortable in all situations
- Variety in colours of same pattern of shoes
- Availability of different patterns of shoes
- Different price range of same brand shoes

d) What types of variations you would prefer in shoes?

- Variety in colours of same pattern of shoes
- Availability of different patterns of shoes
- Different price range of same brand shoes

e) What types of tool of promotion attracts the customer more?

- Advertisement in newspaper, magazines, TV
- Use of famous actor or actress for promotion of shoes
- Direct marketing
- Personal selling

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.478
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	592.083
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

Table 51

Before we check the important factors, it has to be confirmed that whether correlation is existing between the variables or not. To check, KMO and Bartlett's test has to be used. KMO, value should be greater than .5, which shows that samples are taken adequately or not. Thus, in the

present study, .478 has shown that it is adequate but still samples can be increased. Further, Bartlett's test shows whether correlation is existing among variables or not. As, p value, is smaller than 0.05, so it has shown statistically significant correlation in between variables.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Attractive sole	1.000	.554
Reasonable price	1.000	.726
High quality	1.000	.663
Comfortable in all situations	1.000	.585
Variety in colors of same pattern of shoes	1.000	.584
Availability of different patterns of shoes	1.000	.486
Different price range of same brand shoes	1.000	.700

Table 52

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Further, communalities will show to which extent a variable is explained by the component. In present study, only variable which has the lowest communality and further signifies that feature of availability of different patterns of

shoes is less well explained by the analysis than any of the other programs (increasing the number of factors increases the communality of all the variables).

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.660	23.719	23.719	1.660	23.719	23.719	1.621	23.163	23.163
2	1.358	19.401	43.120	1.358	19.401	43.120	1.352	19.311	42.473
3	1.279	18.268	61.388	1.279	18.268	61.388	1.324	18.914	61.388
4	.788	11.253	72.641						
5	.774	11.060	83.701						
6	.679	9.702	93.403						
7	.462	6.597	100.000						

Table 53

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The next table has shown total variance explained, which has shown only three factors (i.e., components). That is, the analysis assumes that the 7 original variables can be reduced to 3 underlying factors. The three components

explain 61% of the variance in the data. That is, when it is assumed that there are three components, we can predict 61% of the information in all the 10 variables.

The first component explains more of the variance than the second component.

Fig. 1

The figure has shown that scree plot which shows that only three components are there whose values are more than 1 that is similar to total variance table. Thus, first three factors are explaining 61% of total features of undertaking factors in study.

Component Matrix

	Component		
	1	2	3
Attractive sole	.719	.035	.190
Reasonable price	.017	-.717	.460
High quality	.371	.700	-.186
Comfortable in all situations	-.635	.118	-.409
Variety in colours of same pattern of shoes	-.322	.460	.518
Availability of different patterns of shoes	.692	.002	-.088
Different price range of same brand shoes	-.144	.355	.744

Table 54

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a. 3 components extracted.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
Attractive sole	.741	.075	-.014
Reasonable price	.185	-.831	.029
High quality	.270	.763	.089
Comfortable in all situations	-.736	.173	-.116
Variety in colors of same pattern of shoes	-.155	.108	.740
Availability of different patterns of shoes	.627	.168	-.254
Different price range of same brand shoes	.088	-.054	.830

Table 55

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

The rotated component matrix, sometimes referred to as the loadings, is the key output of principal components analysis. It contains estimates of the correlations between each of the variables and the estimated components. In present study, there are moderate-to-strong correlations between the expected five improvements of shoes and component.

First component includes

- Attractive sole, Reasonable price, Availability of different patterns of shoes
- High quality
- Different price range of same brand shoes.

The same is visualized with component plot diagram as well, that five components are very close while two are different from those five. Lastly, feature of comfortable and variety in colours are quite close but still no correlation is existing in all the three components.

Component Plot in Rotated Space

Fig. 2

XI. FINDINGS

As per the above analysis, it has been found that according to their occupational position, to analyse the level of priority given to various aspects such as price, durability, and quality by customers when purchasing branded casual and athletic shoes. As a result, characteristics such as prior positive experience and a diverse range of options have a substantial relationship with an individual's professional standing. Because the p value for the Pearson chi-square test is less than 0.01, it can be stated that there is a significant association between age and fashion when it comes to the purchasing of sport shoes on a casual basis. In this sense, it

means that a person's age will influence the type of footwear they purchase. A similar conclusion may be drawn from Phi and Cramer's v test at a significance level of 1%. From KMO and Bartlett's test it has been found that whether there is a correlation between the variables or not KMO and Bartlett's tests must be used to verify. The KMO value should be larger than .5, indicating whether or not samples were taken adequately. Thus, .478, in this investigation, has demonstrated that it is adequate, although samples can still be increased. Furthermore, Bartlett's test determines whether or not there is a correlation between variables. In addition, communalities will reveal how much a variable is explained by a component. Only one variable in the current study has

the lowest communality, implying that the feature of availability of diverse shoe patterns is less effectively explained by the analysis than any of the other programmes (increasing the number of factors increases the communality of all the variables).

REFERENCES

- [1.] Assael, H. (1994). *Consumer behaviour and marketing action*. Mason, OH, United States: Cengage Learning, Inc.
- [2.] Doval, P. (2015, feb 15). *Footwear industry to witness healthy growth, says Assocham*. Retrieved from <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>: <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/Inflation-hits-26-month-low-of-6-55/articleshow/11893806.cms>
- [3.] Dr.S.Saravanan. (2010). A Study on consumer behavior of Women with special reference to Durable goods in Coimbatore city, Tamil Nadu. *indian journal of marketing*.
- [4.] Engel, J. F., Kollat, D. T., & Blackwell, R. D. (1968). *Consumer behavior*. new york: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- [5.] Eric J. Arnould, G. Z. (2004). *consumers*. new york: McGraw-Hill.
- [6.] Euromonitor. (2017, april). *footwear in india*. Retrieved from [euromonitor.com](http://www.euromonitor.com): <http://www.euromonitor.com/footwear-in-india/report>
- [7.] Gupta, A. (2014, jan 27). *Indian Footwear Industry: A Perspective*. Retrieved from [etretail.com](http://retail.economictimes.indiatimes.com) (An initiative of The Economic Times): <http://retail.economictimes.indiatimes.com/retales/indian-footwear-industry-a-perspective/81>
- [8.] J. Paul Peter, J. C. (2010). *Consumer behavior & marketing strategy*. london: McGraw-Hill.
- [9.] jaideep, s. (2016). *Importance of Studying Consumer Behaviour*. Retrieved from [yourarticlelibrary.com](http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com): <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/marketing/consumer-behavior/importance-of-studying-consumer-behaviour/48594/>
- [10.] Jeffrey F. Rayport, B. J. (2004). *Introduction to E-commerce*. McGraw-Hill.
- [11.] John A. Howard, J. N. (1969). *The theory of buyer behavior*. wiley.
- [12.] Kapferer, J.-N. (2008). *The New Strategic Brand Management*. kagon page.
- [13.] Kotler, P. (1994). *arketing Management: Analysis, Planning, Implementation, and Control*. Prentice Hall.
- [14.] Kotler, P. (2009). *Marketing Management*. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [15.] Krugman, H. E. (Autumn, 1965). The Impact of Television Advertising: Learning Without Involvement. *The Public Opinion Quarterly*, 349-356 .
- [16.] kumar, r. (2017). *Top 10 Best Selling Shoes Brands in India 2017*. Retrieved from [scoopHub](http://scoopHub.in): <http://scoopHub.in/top-10-best-shoes-brands-in-india-2016/2/>
- [17.] Lavanya, S. (2016, july 2). *Top 7 Leading Indian Footwear Brands In the Country*. Retrieved from [linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com): <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-7-leading-indian-footwear-brands-country-shruti-lavanya>
- [18.] Michael R. Solomon, G. B. (2006). *Consumer Behaviour: A European Perspective*. Pearson.
- [19.] money matters. (2017). *need for studying consumer behaviour*. Retrieved from <http://accountlearning.com>/[need-studying-consumer-behaviour/](http://accountlearning.com/need-studying-consumer-behaviour/)
- [20.] Nagrale, P. (2015, june 26). *top 15 shoe brand name in india*. Retrieved from [Companies in India](http://companiesinindia.in): <http://companiesinindia.in/shoe-brand-names-in-india/>
- [21.] NICOSIA, F. M. (1966). *Consumer Decision Processes: Marketing and Advertising Implications*. california: Prentice-Hall.
- [22.] Pappas, S. D. (august 1972). A Crucial Test for the Howard-Sheth Model of Buyer Behavior . *Journal of Marketing Research*, 346-348.
- [23.] Philip Kotler, K. L. (2006). *Marketing Management 12e*. U.S.A: Prentice Hall.
- [24.] Roger D. Blackwell, P. W. (2006). *CONSUMER BEHAVIOR*. South-Western: thomson.
- [25.] *Top 10 Best Selling Sports Shoes Brands In India*. (n.d.). Retrieved from [trending top most](http://www.trendingtopmost.com): <http://www.trendingtopmost.com/worlds-popular-list-top-10/2017-2018-2019-2020-2021/product/best-selling-sports-shoes-brands-india-world-market-famous-cheapest-expensive/>
- [26.] Tuck, M. (1976). *How Do We Choose?: A Study in Consumer Behaviour*. Methuen.